

Academic Practices in Selected School of Ormoc City Division

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ABSTRACT

This study sought to determine the socio-demographic profile of the respondents, perceived academic practices by students and teachers, challenges encountered. It involved 221 students and 43 teachers in the School Year 2023-2024, randomly selected by getting 20% from both sex in every grade level. Descriptive method was used using a researcher-made questionnaire. Data was interpreted using frequency tables and chi-square test. Socio-demographic profile in terms of sex was more or less equal. All students went through the same rigors and expected to abide by the academic policies and procedures, 14–16 years old got the highest percentage, majority were from grade eight. Students from this level were more adaptable and compliant compared to other grade level. Students' perception was significantly higher than teachers' perceptions, shown by the chi-square value of 16.985 with a p-value less than .001. Students' value making their own projects and requirements, rarely go to the library for further enrichment on their research article instead of reproducing pages from books. Teachers' responses revealed that students cited proper referencing and citations in their research, the least was that students worked collaboratively in answering assignments before the scheduled date of submission. These findings indicate that students need to embody a passion for research, establish study habits and prepare for examinations and teachers to integrate more collaborative activities with students to enhance collaborative skills, demonstrate initiative, maturity and responsibility. Family and parents posed the greatest challenge. Hence, a caring and supportive family should set forth a motivating and inspiring environment to produce children with academic practices that uphold right values and conduct.

Keywords: *Academic Practices, challenges and collaborative skills*

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INTRODUCTION

Academic practices are defined as completing of academic work with integrity, employing proper referencing and acknowledging all sources (University of Kent, 2022) while academic referencing is often perceived as a straightforward skill, understanding and implementing citation practices can be significantly challenging for students. These challenges are integral to developing academic literacy which plays a crucial role in shaping students' identities as learners and their sense of belonging in higher education (Gravett & Kinchin, 2020).

The National Educators Academy of the Philippines (NEAP, 2024) emphasizes the importance of education that meets learners' needs and equips them with skills relevant to real-world applications underscoring honesty in academic endeavors. Moreover, the MATATAG Curriculum (2019) underscores the importance of honesty among learners, particularly when faced with challenges in understanding instructions.

Demonstrating good values and right conduct in school include the observance of academic practices. It does not come naturally, as this is an internalized process acquired through cultural socialization which includes the influence of people they interact with at home, school and in the community. According to Robson (2019), socialization is an ongoing process of learning the expected behaviors, values, norms and social skills of individuals who occupy particular roles in society. Moreover, there are two categories of socialization: primary socialization and secondary socialization. Primary socialization takes place in the home, when kids initially discover who they are as individuals, pick up language and hone their cognitive abilities. The social education that kids receive when they go to school or other social institutions is referred to as secondary socialization.

Apparently, achieving academic practices involves developing study skills such as reading, note-taking and research. Another is to apply appropriate academic writing in essays, reports or dissertations. One should also observe proper referencing skills as to when and how to cite references to avoid plagiarism. Performing honest examination techniques and possessing critical inquiry and evaluation are considered good academic practices as well (University of Kent, 2021).

Academic practices make each school distinct from the others. Not all schools are the same; however, they aim at developing the learners holistically. Apart from developing good behavior and values, it is also teaching them the required competencies in all the subjects offered in the curriculum. Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) expect their learners to assimilate the necessary skills to be successful in their chosen fields. As mentioned by the University of Edinburgh, it is necessary that students' act in a way that is consistent with the principles of academic good practice and avoid doing anything contrary to the academic-educational objectives. Further, following the principles of good academic practice helps students do schoolwork better (Understanding Good Academic Practice, 2020).

In the Philippines, observing academic practices poses problems in schools, as students face challenges in several academic domains, such as getting high marks during exams, responding critically to questions, or simply understanding lesson content. Students are facing various

challenges in life that may have adverse effects on their academic performance, yet some school programs are not student needs-driven (Dagdag et al. 2019).

In order to better prepare students to become proficient, versatile, well-informed and updated in the 21st century technological skills, the need to implement instructional strategies and activities that naturally align with their predispositions is necessary to make them better learners (Magulod, 2019).

Nowadays, with the advent of technology, the internet offers a wealth of information at our fingertips, including innovations such as Chat Generative Pre-Training Transformer (GPT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Scribbr, Copilot, Neuromorphic technology and more, all products of human creativity and ingenuity (Singh et al., 2021). However, it is essential to approach these technologies with discernment, ensuring their accuracy and reliability. AI has undoubtedly enhanced human capabilities, yet it cannot replace the vital role of teachers, who serve as mentors and role models to students, influencing their development profoundly.

Moreover, in its new educational context, artificial intelligence (AI) “is a part of our lives. Everything that we do on the internet is influenced to various extents by AI. It can automate various tasks in education as well as in other domains. When a new promising technology emerges and the limitations of the technology and the challenges of applying it are often not perfectly understood, then the technology may seem to open radically new possibilities for solving old problems” (Singh et al., 2021).

Hence, observing academic practices at Linao National High School among the students is a great challenge. Based on the records of the school guidance office, a number of students were referred for academic counseling or coaching due to underachievement, failures, low performance in periodicals, quizzes, assignments and lacking skills in research. With this guidance information, it is imperative to look into the sources of students’ academic-related problems and come up with measures and parameters for students to develop the necessary skills and competencies, inclusive of academic practices.

This study further behooves the school by achieving and upholding good academic practices among the students. On the other hand, it will give insights to the teachers and staff regarding the level of academic practices of students at Linao National High School. This study will help the guidance office develop a program enhancing academic practices of its students.

Research Questions

The study aims to determine the level of academic practices in selected school of Ormoc City Division specifically the Junior High School students of Linao National High School, Ormoc City, Leyte. It seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the socio- demographic profile of students in terms of the following:
 - 1.1 Sex
 - 1.2 Age
 - 1.3 Grade Level

2. What is the level of academic practices of the students at Linao National High School as perceived by the students and teachers?
3. What are the challenges encountered by students concerning academic practices related to:
 - 3.1 School
 - 3.2 Family
 - 3.3 Peer
4. What is the level of extent of academic challenges between students' and teachers?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile and level of academic practices of the students at Linao National High School as perceived by the students' respondents and teachers?
6. Is there a significant difference between the perception of students and teachers on academic practices in Linao National High School?
7. What action plan can be designed to enhance academic practices?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed quantitative research using the descriptive survey method of research to measure the academic practices among students of Linao National High School, determine the socio-demographic profile of the respondents, such as sex, age, and grade level, the level of academic practices among students as perceived by students and teachers and determine the significant difference between the perceptions of students and teachers on academic practices.

The Sample and Local of the Study

This study was conducted at Linao National High School, Linao, Ormoc City, Leyte, during the academic year 2023-2024, using random sampling. According to Hayes (2023), a simple random sample takes a small, random portion of the entire population to represent the entire data set, where each member or participant has an equal probability of being chosen.

The respondents of the study consist of 20%, or equivalently, 221 Junior High School students officially enrolled this school year (2023-2024). They were randomly selected by getting 20% from the males as well as the females in every grade level. Another respondents of the study are the 43 or equivalent to 80%, Junior High School teachers of Linao National High School, they were randomly selected. Table 1 below shows the number of respondents of the study.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

<i>Respondent</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample Size</i>
A. Student	1106	221
B. Teachers	54	43
Total	1309	291

Research Instrument

The instrument used was a research-made questionnaire in a form of a survey to gather the needed data. The draft of the questionnaire was drawn out based on the researcher's readings and published researches relevant to the study. Revision and refinement of the questionnaire were done upon the recommendations and approval by the panel of examiners and the Dean of the graduate school. Pilot testing was done before the conduct of the study.

The survey questionnaire for the students has three parts: Part I gathers data on the socio-demographic profile of the students based on sex, age, and grade level. Part II measures the level of academic practices as perceived by the students and teachers. It consists of 15 indicators where students rated as (4) always practiced, (3) moderately practiced, (2) rarely practiced and (1) never practiced. The survey questionnaire delves into the level of academic practices when taking quizzes, examinations, assignments, projects, and research work. Part III is on challenges encountered by students concerning academic practices, which were categorized into school-related challenges, family-related challenges, and parents, as well as peer-related challenges. Again, the data collected was tallied, tabulated, and interpreted. Lastly, Part IV was for the teachers' respondents, which posed some queries as to how students preserved academic practices in their classes. For complete anonymity, responses were coded, tallied, and interpreted.

Gathering of Data

Before the conduct of the study, permission was sought from the school administrator of Linao National High School. Upon approval of the school head, it was forwarded to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Ormoc City Division, Ormoc City, Leyte. A letter was sent to the teachers' respondents and the students' respondents. After the permit was granted, the researcher administered the instruments to the randomly selected respondents during their vacant time on the scheduled date after being oriented on the purpose of the study. The allocated time for completion is 20 minutes.

The responses of the respondents were then tallied and tabulated. After tabulation, it was presented to the statistician for interpretation.

The data gathered was subjected to a reliability index to ascertain the validity and reliability of the test. Respondents of the study were assured of the confidentiality of the results as part of the ethics of research.

It involved descriptive analysis and interpretation of the respondent's socio-demographic profile, the extent of academic practices, and the challenges encountered with such practices. Quantitative descriptions were employed in this study using percentages, ranks, weighted mean, and chi-square test. The method was utilized to generate information about situations and conditions regarding academic practices. The demographic profile of students in terms of personal that include sex, age, and grade level was measured through simple frequency and percentage counts.

To determine the level of academic practices, weighted means were computed, and students' responses were categorized or leveled into Always Practiced (4), Moderately Practiced (3), Rarely Practiced (2), and Never Practiced (1).

The computed weighted mean was then categorized as follows:

Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Descriptions
3.25 – 4.00	Always Practiced	The indicators were consistently and excellently practiced.
2.50 – 3.24	Moderately Practiced	The practice of the indicators was not consistently done.
1.75 – 2.49	Rarely Practiced	The vindicators were fairly practiced.
1.00 – 1.74	Never Practiced	The practiced of the indicators were not done.

On the relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and the level of academic practices, a Chi Square test was employed. On the other hand, for challenges encountered, the responses of the respondents were tallied and ranked according to their choice and preference. The simple frequency and percentage count were considered. Below is the range of percentage and its category and interpretation.

% of Responses	Extent of Challenges	Interpretation
89- 100 %	Very High Extent	Most challenging
60- 79%	Moderate Extent	More challenging
30- 59%	Little Extent	Less challenging
10- 29 %	No Extent	Not challenging

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results of the survey on academic practices among Junior High School students of Linao National High School. This section provides answers to the research questions of the study, which include the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, and grade level, the level of academic practices, and challenges in observing academic practices. Moreover, all necessary data are in tabular form and are further supported by the appropriate statistical interpretations.

Socio-demographic Profile of the Students

Table 2 presents the demographic profile of the respondents, which comprises their sex, age, and grade level.

Demographic information provides data regarding research participants and is necessary for the determination of whether the individuals in a particular study are a representative sample of the target population for generalization purposes.

Sex. This refers to male or female in the study.

It can be gleaned and noted from the table, in terms of sex, both males and females were equally represented, which is almost equal and equivalent to 50%. Based on the data provided by the school records, the total population enrolled for both males and females were almost equal. This implied that the twenty percent (20%) random sample of the study is a good representative of the whole population of the Junior High School of Linao National High School, which is 1,106 with a total of 551 or 50% officially enrolled male students and 555 or 50% officially enrolled female students a matter of four students. The school record shows that in this school year, there were almost the same number of enrolled students in terms of sex, either male or female.

This result is aligned with the concept of gender equality and equity adhering to Gender and Development (GAD) advocacy, which is equal rights for everyone in education.

Gender equality in education benefits every child. Equal rights and opportunities for girls and boys help all children fulfill their potential. While gender-equitable education systems empower girls and boys and promote the development of life skills like self-management, communication, negotiation, and critical thinking, young people need to succeed (UNICEF, n.d.). Moreover, Republic Act (RA) 11650, also known as the Inclusion Policy for Learners with Disabilities is a Philippine law promoting inclusive education and protecting the rights of learners with disabilities to quality education, health care, and rehabilitation services, while establishing support centers and coordinating agencies to ensure their inclusion and well-being (Republic Act No. 11650, n.d.).

Age. Another variable in the study is the age of the respondents. In the same table presented, of the 221 respondents, those aged 14–16 got the highest percentage, equivalent to 112 respondents, or 51%. It was followed by aged 12–13, with 99 respondents, or 45%. Most of them were usually from grades eight and seven. Lastly, the 17–19-year-old respondents, with a total of ten (10) respondents, or equivalent to 10% were from Grades nine and ten.

The age description indicated denotes that these students were considered over-aged. Students who were over-aged as reflected in the School Form-1 (SF-1) records were returnees who did not enroll in the previous years for some personal reasons or repeaters who dropped from the last school year they attended.

Table 2. Socio-demographic profile of students

Sex	Frequency	%	p-value
Male	110	50%	1.000
Female	111	50%	
Total	221	100%	
Age			
12-13	99	45%	<.001
14-16	112	51%	
17-19	10	5%	
Total	221	100%	
Mean Age = 13.86 years; SD = 1.439			
Grade Level			
Grade 7	51	23%	<.001
Grade 8	61	28%	
Grade 9	53	24%	
Grade 10	56	25%	
Total	221	100%	

Note: P-values less than 0.05 means the proportions are significantly different.

As identified by Parreño (2019), one of the reasons for students to drop out from school is the distant school's location, no school within the barangay, no regular transport, housekeeping, marriage, employment, lack of personal interest, inability to cope with school work, and poverty. These reasons may also be applicable to students who are returnees.

On the good side, the Department of Education has the Philippine Education for All (EFA) of 2015 and onwards, which has a vision and a holistic program of reforms that aims at improving the quality of basic education for every Filipino learner. EFA's objectives are: to provide education options for all out-of-school adults and young people; encourage the completion of a full cycle of basic schooling to a satisfactory level at every grade by all Filipino children; and to commit to the attainment of basic education competencies for everyone. With this program, over-aged students

were given a chance to be admitted to the school and continue to avail themselves of their right to education.

Over-aged students enrolled in Linao National High School were taken care of by the Learners Enhancement Action Program of the school (LEAP), whose goal is to conduct review or remedial classes in order for the students to pass the Philippine Educational Placement Test (PEPT), a test under the Accreditation and Equivalency Program (A&E Program - Executive Order No. 733, s. 1981). The objectives of PEPT are to establish that students have met learning standards for specific grade levels, to determine the appropriate grade level of learners in special circumstances in the formal school system, and to assess competencies in academic areas for entry or reentry to formal school. (Department of Education, 2015 and onwards).

Grade level. This is another variable included in the socio-demographic profile. As revealed in the table, grade eight got the highest number of students, equivalent to 28%, followed by grade ten at 25%, grade nine at 24%, and the least was grade seven with 23% of respondents. Grade eight level got the highest number of enrollees because, as per school's previous enrollment data, grade seven in the school year 2022-2023 has the highest population. This means that many students were promoted to the eighth-grade level this school year.

The gathered data connotes that, based on the school's enrollment data for the school year 2023-2024, grade seven has the least number of enrollees. Factors affecting the decreasing population of the grade 7 enrolment as per the Early Registration Mapping of the out of school youth or out of school aged learners and findings from the school's Monitoring Evaluation and Adjustment (SMEA 2023–2024) These reasons contributed to the decrease of enrollment in grade seven, most evidently is the creation, birth, and existence of integrated schools (elementary and high school) in the barangay where elementary schools and learners are encouraged to enroll in adjacent barangay schools, thus, resulting in a decrease in enrollment and leading to practicality purposes.

This level of academic practices, as perceived by teachers' respondents, are common observations in teachers' daily grind of teaching. Staying in the school for several years has made them more acquainted with students' attitudes towards academic practices.

Level of academic practices of the students at Linao National High School as Perceived by Students

Result on the level of academic practices as perceived by the students is described as "Moderately Practiced" with a mean of 2.97. This result is attributed to the fact that from 15 indicators, ten of these were claimed to Moderately Practiced, four Always Practiced and one Rarely Practiced.

As to the indicator rated by students as Always Practiced with a mean of 3.51, the indicator is on making their own projects and requirements. This result is based on the data, where 144 students claimed to always make their own projects and requirements. This implies that students are responsible for their school projects and requirements. As a result of this right attitude, they

are considered students with autonomy and liberty and have less supervision needed, which denotes that they initiate to work independently.

Among the 15 academic practices done by the students', the top three were making their own projects and requirements, preparing for quizzes and examinations, understanding test directions, and confidently answering the test. In the grading system of the Department of Education, 40% were allotted to performance tasks and written works; these include projects and other requirements that they comply with for them to get 40% of their grade, and in fact, students are indeed aware of this policy. When it came to quizzes and examinations as one of the components in the basis of giving grades, the department itself set standards for this examination (scheduled examination) rather than on unannounced quizzes or quizzes, even exams or chapter tests given by teachers. Test, measurement, and evaluation as a course and as part and parcel of any curriculum stressed that the giving of instructions to students should be clear and even adhere to the principle of SMART (Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Realistic, and Time Bound(ed)).

On the other hand, going to the library for further enrichment on their research article instead of producing a page of a book was the least among the 15 indicators, where only 43 students claimed doing it was always practiced. Visiting the library is probably given less importance nowadays because students have easy access to technology. Tabassum et al, (2019) gave details about how the school libraries support teaching and learning with the best available information resources. This somehow affects and influences the present generation's use of the internet, where information is just a click away.

Table 3. Level of academic practices of the students at Linao National High School as perceived by students

	Academic Practices	Weighted Mean	Level
1.	I make my own projects and requirements.	3.51	Always Practiced
2.	I prepare myself for quizzes and examinations.	3.37	Always Practiced
3.	I understand test directions and confidently answer the test.	3.34	Always Practiced
4.	I answer on my own some difficult or challenging assignments.	3.30	Always Practiced
5.	I memorize and do mnemonics as my study technique before the schedule of examination.	3.12	Moderately Practiced
6.	I make my own essay work even after reading articles from the textbooks.	3.03	Moderately Practiced
7.	I paraphrased research notes from the internet.	2.94	Moderately Practiced
8.	I can answer independently questions asked during class recitation and oral examination.	2.90	Moderately Practiced

9.	I work collaboratively with my classmates in answering assignments before the scheduled date of submission.	2.89	Moderately Practiced
10.	I rephrase the sentence from an internet article with proper citation of author and main topic.	2.87	Moderately Practiced
11	I solve math assignments critically and independently using the help of technology.	2.88	Moderately Practiced
12.	I enjoy working on assigned reflections and journal.	2.86	Moderately Practiced
13.	I am capable of answering announced and unannounced test.	2.76	Moderately Practiced
14.	I cite proper references and citations in my research	2.65	Moderately Practiced
15.	I go to the library for further enrichment on my research article instead of reproducing a page of a book.	2.19	Rarely Practiced
Overall Mean		2.97	Moderately Practiced

Legend: 1.00–1.74 *Never Practiced* 1; 1.75–2.49 *Rarely Practiced*; 2.50–3.24 *Moderately Practiced*; 3.25 – 4.00 *Always Practiced*

Some students at Linao National High School have acquired smartphones or Android phones especially during the pandemic. They find it very useful during their online classes. In an interview and in real-life interactions, they mentioned using their phones for research, communication, and friend connections. As a result, using the library was less valued. This minimally significant recourse to copying a page from a book and providing references and citations repeatedly comes down to the existence and introduction of technology, namely the use of a smartphone or other mobile device as a tool or medium for a variety of school assignments in the classroom.

This is in contrast to the study of Reddy (2021), what the world enjoys today is the by and end product of research, thus students need to improve or value research work. In addition, Fatemi (2020) added that Support Programs to teach students about the attribution and proper ways of referencing is necessary.

Library as a heart in any academe or learning institution play significant role in shaping the mind and learning necessary skills (American Association of school Librarians, 2020). It supports to the study of (Kachel, 2020), library supports information literacy, provide with students with a wealth of resources, foster an atmosphere that students can collaborate and pursue independent and solitude when they study. Library indeed foster an atmosphere that encourages the love of reading and life-long learning. When you read, you will be loaded with many information. It may not lead to mediocrity, one can be full of knowledge and wisdom, you can be sharp and smart.

This level of Academic Practices as perceived by teachers' respondents are common observations in teachers' daily grind of teaching. Staying in the school for several years have made them more acquainted with student's attitude towards academic practices.

The highest indicator rated by teachers as Moderately practiced, with a mean of 2.72, is that students cited proper referencing and citations in their research. Followed by 2.69, where students paraphrased research notes from the internet and rephrased the sentence from an internet article with proper citation of the author and main topic. Results showed that students demonstrated skill in citing references, this implied that the students understood the value and importance of acknowledging the work of others. This further implied that the teachers had taught the students this content, which the students were able to internalize. In the Classroom Observation Tool (COT) of the Department of Education, it encourages every teacher to integrate lessons across learning areas as long as it doesn't go beyond the context and content of the lessons. This can be the Privacy Act and certain provisions on plagiarism, patenting, and copyright. Intellectual property rights, in the bigger picture, should be inculcated in the minds and thoughts of every learner.

As to the indicators rated Rarely Practiced, eleven out of fifteen indicators were described as Rarely Practiced. The least among these academic practices was on students who worked collaboratively in answering assignments before the scheduled date of submission.

This result is based on teachers' observations that students' collaboration is rarely practiced due to factors such as a lack of time management skills, an individualistic culture in educational environments, an insufficient understanding of the benefits of collaboration, technology obstacles that prevent group work outside of the classroom, and insufficient chances offered by teachers.

In the Department of Education alone Collaborative Expertise (CE) are sought. In the presence of their daily grind of teaching, learning action cell where teachers convene for a relevant matter to tackle to this may include, teaching pedagogies, update and upgrade of one's skills and capability among others. Thus, students' approaches to learning and their collaboration with classmates and peers contribute academic achievement (Han et al., 2023).

Level of academic practices of the students at Linao National High School as perceived by teachers

Table 3.1 Level of Academic Practices Perceived by Teachers

Academic Practices	Weighted Mean	Level
1. My students cited proper referencing and citations in their research.	2.72	Moderately Practiced
2. My students paraphrased research notes from internet	2.69	Moderately Practiced
3. My students rephrased the sentence from an internet article with proper citation of author and main topic.	2.56	Moderately Practiced
4. My students went to the library for further enrichment on their research article instead of reproducing a page of a book.	2.44	Rarely Practiced
5. My students memorized and do mnemonics as them study technique before the schedule of examination.	2.26	Rarely Practiced
6. My students are capable of answering announced and unannounced test.	2.23	Rarely Practiced
7. My students made their own essay work even after reading articles from the textbooks.	2.21	Rarely Practiced
8. My students answered on their own some difficult or challenging assignments.	2.09	Rarely Practiced
9. My students solved math assignments critically and independently using technology.	2.07	Rarely Practiced
10. My students understood test directions and confidently answered the test.	2.02	Rarely Practiced
11. My students enjoyed working on assigned reflections and journal.	2.02	Rarely Practiced
12. My students could answer independently questions asked during class recitation and oral examination.	1.98	Rarely Practiced
13. My students prepared their selves for quizzes and examinations.	1.91	Rarely Practiced
14. My students made their own projects and requirements.	1.86	Rarely Practiced
15. My students worked collaboratively in answering assignments before the schedule date of submission.	1.72	Never Practiced
Overall Mean	2.18	Rarely Practiced

Legend: 1.00–1.74 Never Practiced; 1.75–2.49 Rarely Practiced; 2.50–3.24 Moderately Practiced; 3.25 – 4.00 Always Practiced

Moreover, terms like pedagogy, andragogy, heutagogy and peeragogy are now at stake when it comes to phases of learning. Their usage should be stimulated in teaching-learning process, collaborative and engagement learning improve students' academic development (Qureshi, et al., 2021). The lowest were students who made their own projects and requirements, and students worked collaboratively in answering assignments before the scheduled date of submission.

In today's age of artificial intelligence and other technological tools such as Gemini, Scribbr, Neuromorphic, Quillbot, and Grammarly, learning and accessing information is just a click away. This ease of access may lead students to rely heavily on these tools, potentially diminishing their initiative to engage deeply in self-directed projects and collaborative efforts.

The educational principles of “education for all” and “no one will be left behind” aims to provide equal learning opportunities, but it can inadvertently contribute to a lack of emphasis on developing collaborative skills. Teachers' anecdotal records further highlight that many students are becoming increasingly lazy and tardy, often spending more time on social media platforms like TikTok and Facebook rather than focusing on their studies. This trend reflects a broader issue where the convenience of technology and the emphasis on individual achievement undermine the importance of collaborative learning and personal initiative.

Table 3.2 Summary of Students Academic Practices as perceived by students and teachers

Respondents	Mean	Description
Students	2.97	Moderately Practiced
Teachers	2.18	Rarely Practiced

For the students' respondents claimed to be moderately practiced when it came to making their own projects and requirements, preparing themselves for quizzes and examinations, understanding test directions, and confidently answering the test, but rarely practiced when it came to going to the library for further enrichment on research articles instead of reproducing a page of a book. These impacted, however, guidance programs and services on its campaign on digital citizenship and literacy, plus the fact that these were integrated in the lessons on music, arts, physical education, and health (MAPEH) and “Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao” (EsP) and across the curriculum or learning area. These data were validated through an interview, and they expressed that students were very aware as to how articles on the internet and the world wide web were to be of good use, hence rarely practiced in collaboration.

According to the students themselves, their academic practices fall closer to the middle of the scale. A mean score of 2.97 suggested that students perceived their academic practices as moderately practiced. This implied that while students engaged in academic practices, there was room for improvement or variability in their consistency. In contrast, teachers perceived students' academic practices as lower on the scale. A mean score of 2.18 indicates that teachers believed

students rarely practiced these academic practices. This perception suggested a significant discrepancy between how students perceived their academic practices and how teachers viewed them.

These data were validated through an interview with the teachers' respondents. They expressed that when it came to making projects and requirements for students, preparing themselves for quizzes and examinations, understanding test directions, confidently answering the test, and answering on their own some difficult or challenging assignments, the teacher's level of these academic practices was fair, while for the students, these were interpreted as always practiced.

There might be factors influencing the different perceptions of students and teachers regarding academic practices. This leads to certain actions and procedures that are viewed differently by students and teachers. According to Amerstorfer and Von Münster-Kistner (2021), students' academic engagement depends on a variety of factors that are related to personal characteristics, the teacher, the teaching methodology, peers, and other features in the learning environment.

In addition, teachers' attitudes toward their students have been associated with differential teachers' expectations and, in turn, with students' educational pathways. (Cate and Glock, 2019),

Obtrusive observation is a manifestation of how students' actions on projects, requirements, and other factors are a living testament to how students behave and act in the four corners of the classroom. Students' physical presence for eight (8) hours is an evident as to how students do their tasks inside the school premises. An adviser is encouraged to know very well his or her students'; this can be done in the form of or in the presence of anecdotal records, home visit reports, and class attendance, among others. On the other hand, students were encouraged to collaborate, engage, and establish good rapport with classmates and peers so as not to jeopardize quality learning. Even if it is a group or collaboration, the individual is still held accountable for his or her actions.

While on making their own essay work even after reading articles from the textbook, paraphrasing research notes from the internet, and answering independently asked questions during class recitation and oral examination, solving math assignments critically and independently using the help of technology, enjoying working on assigned reflections and journals, and being capable of answering announced and unannounced tests, the teachers' respondents level of these academic practices was fair, while for the students, these were interpreted as moderately practiced.

Peer collaboration is encouraged by teachers, who believe that mediocrity is unacceptable. Thus, aiming for greatness should always be the goal. The students viewed the above indicators as somewhat practiced because they were instructed to do so. The fact that the performance assignment accounts for 40% of the Department of Education's grading system alone provides compelling proof of these efforts.

Extent of Challenges Encountered by students concerning Academic Practices in School related, Family and Parents and Peers

This section presents some of the challenges encountered by the respondents concerning academic practices, whether in school, family, parents, or peers. These factors consist of sub-indicators that pose challenges among the students' respondents in practicing, observing, and demonstrating academic practices.

The challenges encountered by students concerning academic practices were categorized into school related, family related, and peer related.

School Related Challenges.

For school related, there were five challenges used to measure this factor. The total percentage of responses to the school related challenges was 74% with Moderate Extent for difficult subjects, followed by teachers expecting high scores on the test after the discussion of 59% with Little Extent who said yes. The least was the high standard of instructions of 42% with Little Extent saying yes.

The most challenging for students in their academic practices are the difficult subjects; this indicates that a significantly majority of students struggle with challenging subjects. Facing this academic challenge significantly impacts students' academic performance, self-esteem, and future opportunities, particularly in STEM fields. The fact that there were eight subjects offered in the curriculum of the Department of Education, Science, and Technology, English and Math were considered precursor subjects in other minor subjects; hence, it should be mastered by the learners.

Table 4. Extent of challenges encountered by students concerning academic practices

Challenges	F	% of Responses	Extent of Challenges
School Related:			
1. Difficult subjects	163	74%	Moderate Extent
2. Teachers expect high scores on the test after the discussion	130	59%	Little Extent
3. Honors / recognition or rank to be maintained	121	55%	Little Extent
4. Cannot anymore study because of too many assignments/ activities to do everyday	98	44%	Little Extent
5. High Standard of instructions	93	42%	Little Extent
Average		55%	Moderate Extent
Family and Parents:			
1. Parents' expectations	178	81%	Very High Extent

2.	Parents/ relatives are alumni of the school you are currently enrolled	91	41%	Little Extent
3.	Sibling comparison	89	40%	Little Extent
4.	Reputation of parents	82	37%	Little Extent
5.	Parents are high achiever during high school	75	34%	Little Extent
	Average		47%	Little Extent
	Peer Related:			
1.	Competitive classmates	165	75%	Moderate Extent
2.	Comparing scores from other students	125	57%	Little Extent
3.	Scores are publicly displayed by a classmate	92	42%	Little Extent
4.	Belongs to a top section	70	32%	Little Extent
5.	Bullying (if the student got low score)	49	22%	Not Affected
	Average		45%	Little Extent
	Overall		43%	Little Extent

In addition, the Department of Education MATATAG curriculum (2019) recognized the learning gaps or subject area deficiencies of the students; hence, DepEd mandated all public and private high schools to conduct remedial and advancement classes during summer for the K to 12 Basic Education Program. This is in support of the delivery of the National Learning Camp (NLC, 2022). To group learners into enhancement and advanced learners in reading and numeracy. This will further address the gap and augment learning poverty for learners for them to become literate and numerate.

The results of the Programme International Student Assessment (PISA, 2019) in English, specifically in Reading Comprehension, Science, and Mathematics (ESM), have been found to be low when it comes to the academic performance of learners (Juan, 2019). From the many hearts of curriculum, which is the core and brain to address this gap, namely the Revised Basic Education Curriculum (RBEC), K–12 Program, or RA 10533, currently the MATATAG curriculum aims to address learning poverty from congested curriculum to decongest the curriculum and that it stressed out to simplify and localize as well as to tailor and address individual instruction, considering diverse types of learners possessing different and multiple intelligences.

Family and Parents Challenges

The results showed that parents' expectations were the most challenging for students, and this was rated to a very high extent. The family and parents as the main support system of the learners parents expectations got highest of 81% 178 responses with Very High Extent, while the lowest was parents were high achiever during high school with a score of 34% with Little Extent

Parents play a very crucial role in the development of their kids as the first teachers of their sons and daughters, or their learners. This is indeed shared leadership and responsibility between internal and external stakeholders. This has been stipulated in the mission of DepEd, which states,

“Family, community, and other stakeholder holders are actively engaged and share responsibility for developing life-long learners.” Family as the backbone and main source of strengths and weaknesses, where the students shall be supported and where they source out their strengths and strong support systems. Undeniably, the role of family and parents has been very significant. These pose a challenge nowadays, where the digital world is now a means of recreation and expression of oneself; thus, this will lead to a gap in communication with family and significant others. Parental pressure is the drive that parents put on their children to achieve a a certain goal. On the other hand, students's self-efficacy is their belief that they can successfully complete a task, whatever challenge it is (Moneva et al., 2020).

Learners are supposed to be encourage and motivated, thus one should start where his or her capability is, interest and capacity. He/she should have or possess a supportive, caring and learning environment. Parental expectation, when perceived as pressure and challenges decrease well-being it increase anxiety and depression among adolescents (Jiang, et.al. 2022).

Peer Related

On this challenge, the competitive classmates got the highest number of responses who said “yes” with 75. Little extent, the data revealed that learners were not bullied during examinations, and if they got low scores, 49 students responded with a moderate extent. Inclusive education is now the educational paradigm where learners are to be part of the mainstream, hence non-discrimination. This is indeed a challenge; every learner is a responsibility, and no child will be left behind. This supports the study of Kang et al. (2024). Despite on the recognition of the impact of peer relationships, learning motivation, and learning engagement on academic achievement, thus improving peer relationships, learning motivation, and learning engagement.

In the philosophy that “No man is an island” and that every individual needs to socialize with each other. In the case of the students’ lives, friends and peers play a significant role in their lives. As the saying goes, “High school life is the best stage of one’s student’s life.” As such, life is to be enjoyed with fun and memories with peers. Hence, “the best memories in life are made with high school friends” (unknown).

Significant relationship between demographic- profile & level of academic practices of the students at Linao National High School as perceived by the respondents and teachers

Table 5. Relationship between the demographic profile and level of academic practices of the students at Linao National High School as perceived by the students (n=221)

Comparison		χ^2 – value	df	Degree of Relationship	p- value	Significance
Level of academic Practices	Sex	6.059	3	0.163	0.109	Not Significant
	Age	18.584	21	0.279	0.612	Not Significant
	Grade Level	18.484	9	0.278	0.030	Significant

The result of the significant relationship between the demographic profile and level of academic practices of the students of Linao National High School, with a total population of 221, the data showed no significant relationship between sex and age. As to the grade level of academic practice for grades seven (7) and ten (10), it has a significant relationship when it comes to academic practices. This supports the study by Malone et al. (2020), which found that there was an impact of grade level assignments on kids' mental, social, and emotional growth as they transitioned from elementary to middle school.

The significant Difference between the perception of students and teachers on academic practices

Table 6. Significant Difference between the perception of students and teachers on academic practices

Respondent		Perception				Total
		1	2	3	4	
Student	Count	4.000	50.000	86.000	81.000	221.000
	Expected count	3.348	49.390	97.106	71.155	221.000
Teacher	Count	0.000	9.000	30.000	4.000	43.000
	Expected count	0.652	9.610	18.894	13.845	43.000
Total	Count	4.000	59.000	116.000	85.000	264.000
	Expected count	4.000	59.000	116.000	85.000	264.000

Chi-square value = 16.985; df=3; p-value= <.001

Findings of the study revealed that there was a significant difference on the perceptions of students and teachers about academic practices. That the perception of students on the academic practices was significantly higher than the perceptions of teachers since students had a higher mean academic practices rating. This implied that teachers and students do not have the same perception in terms of the observance of academic practices in school. There is a significant difference between the perceptions of students and teachers on academic practices, as shown in Chi-square value of 16.985 with p-value less than .001.

Proposed Action Plan to Enhance Academic Practices

In line with the findings of the study, an action plan is designed to enhance academic practices for all students at Linao National High School. Academic practices shall be continuously observed because it is very vital that one demonstrate and observe this, which includes study skills such as note-taking, writing essays, research, academic writing, and proper referencing, among others. Performing honest examination techniques and possessing critical inquiry and evaluation

are considered good academic practices as well. Currently, the Department of Education aims for learners to possess 21st Century skills that include communication, collaboration, creativity, and critical thinking, among others. The level of academic practices as perceived by the students and teachers and the challenges encountered by the respondents in preserving academic practices paved the way to designing an action plan. The school administrators, faculty, and staff may improve and enhance the plan in order to have an effective culture of good academic practices in the school. This will serve as a benchmark for other schools to improve and design a plan appropriate to the needs of their specific school. The designed plans, with the support of the school's valued internal and external stakeholders, will hopefully and progressively develop students' academic practices. A detailed presentation of the proposed action plan is found in the Appendix section.

CONCLUSION

Summary of Findings

This study was conducted to determine the academic practices level of students' at Linao National High School. The main instrument used in this study was a researcher-made questionnaire, which was tested and answered by 221 students and 43 selected teachers, regardless of their teaching position and experience.

Findings of the study showed that those aged 14–16 had the highest total population, which was equivalent to 51%. In terms of sex, there were almost an equal number of respondents. In terms of grade level, grade eight students got the highest percentage of respondents.

The results on the level of academic practices among the students' of Linao National High School in terms of indicators, students make their own projects and requirements, prepare for quizzes and examinations, understand test directions and confidently answer the test of their own got the highest level and were interpreted as Always Practiced.

While on the teachers' respondents, results showed that the highest among the indicators were that students cited proper referencing and citations in their research, students paraphrased research notes from the internet, students rephrased the sentences from the internet article with proper citation of the author and main topic.

On the challenges encountered by students concerning academic practices, school related per se was on difficult subjects ranked first; for family and parent challenges, parents' expectations got the highest result; and for peer-related challenges, competitive classmates were on the zenith.

There was a non-significant relation between level of academic practices and sex means. That level of academic practices of respondents does not differ when grouped according to sex. There were significant relations between level of academic practices and grade level, which means that the level of academic practices of respondents differs when grouped according to grade level

using the Chi-square test. Grade eight respondents had the highest mean rank, while Grade ten got the lowest mean rank, that is, Grade eight respondents have the highest level of academic practices.

The challenges that students encountered in preserving academic practices in terms of school related challenges were difficult subjects and high standards of instruction. For family and parent challenges, parents' expectations and whether parents or relatives were alumni of the school where learners were currently enrolled were the highest among the given challenges.

For peer related challenges, competitive classmates and comparing scores from other students have a moderate extent among the challenges. Findings revealed that there was a significant difference in the perceptions of students and teachers about academic practices. That the perception of students on academic practices was significantly higher than the perceptions of teachers since students had a higher mean academic practices rating. This implied that teachers and students do not have the same perception in terms of the observance of academic practices in school. There is a significant difference between the perceptions of students and teachers on academic practices at Linao National High School, as shown by the chi-square value of 16.985 with a p-value less than .001.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that the almost equal representation of male and female respondents in the study showed gender balance. This implied that, regardless of sex, all students at Linao National High School went through the same rigors of academic practices and were expected to abide by the academic policies and procedures of the school. Grade eight students were more adaptable and compliant with the academic practices and policies compared to other grade levels. Among the challenges encountered, family and parents posed a very challenging encountered by students concerning academic practices. Hence, a caring and supportive family should set forth a motivating and inspiring environment to produce children with academic practices that uphold the right values and conduct.

Recommendations

In light of the conclusions, the following items are herein recommended:

1. Implement a guidance program and enhance academic practices among all bona fide students of Linao National High School, ensuring inclusivity, gender equality, equity and enhance good study habits;
2. Intensify group collaboration, group work, and activities adhering to the principle of "group collaboration but individual accountability."
3. Integrate in the lesson exemplar or lesson script intellectual property rights that include plagiarism, copyright, and patenting in all academic endeavors and increase teacher to student contact time;
4. Conduct a research congress, convention, forum, or colloquium to inculcate a love of research work and instill the value of good academic practices. Update and upgrade the

state-of-the-art facilities, like a strong internet connection and advanced school multimedia facilities, to encourage students to visit the digital library ; and

5. Adopt the proposed program subject to localization, contextualization as well as tailor the need of students and teachers in the ground and on the field.

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